

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART I. GENERAL STUDY OF THE RICINUS LIPASE FROM CASTOR SEEDS

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The effect of different factors like the nature of the buffer, the effect of concentration of the buffer, substrate and enzyme on the activity of ricinus lipase from castor seed has been studied. An attempt has been made to prepare lipase which keeps its activity fairly constant for an appreciably long time.

Reynolds Green (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1890, B, 48, 370) discovered the enzyme, Ricinus lipase (*Ricinus communis*) present in the castor seed. Willstätter and Waldschmidt (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1923-24, 134, 161) found that the optimum pH for the ricinus lipase from castor seed was between 4.7 and 5.0, varying slightly according to the buffer used. Tanaka (Eighth Int. Congress of Applied Chemistry, 1912, Sec. Vd, 11, 37 ; *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1912, 31, 884) prepared the lipase powder from castor seed. Longnecker and Haly (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2019) modified Tanaka's method and prepared an active lipase powder.

As it is felt that 'lipase' can be used as a hydrolysing agent to hydrolyse oils in the soap industry as well as a synthetic agent to prepare synthetic fat, a detailed survey was undertaken to study the different oil seeds available in India for their lipolytic activity and the feasibility of obtaining a cheap and active lipase on a large scale. First of all, the lipolytic activity of castor seed was studied in detail.

EXPERIMENTAL

The lipase powder was prepared from fresh "well ripened castor seeds" by Longnecker and Haly's method (*loc. cit.*). The fine powder obtained was preserved in a bottle after adding few drops of toluene to prevent bacterial action and used for the present work.

The different factors which control the activity of the lipase have been investigated by studying the hydrolysis of olive oil by ricinus lipase from castor seeds under different conditions.

Effect of the Nature of the Buffer on the Optimum pH of the Ricinus Lipase.
—Disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer mixtures of different pH were prepared according to McIlvaine's method (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, 49, 183) and sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer mixtures of different pH according to Walpole's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 2501, 2521).

The hydrolysis of olive oil by ricinus lipase was carried out at different pH using different buffer mixtures.

Each set of experiments consisted of olive oil (1 c. c.), water (2 c. c.), lipase (0.1 g.), and 5 c. c. of buffer of varying pH value and a few drops of toluene in a conical flask. It was corked well and incubated for 24 hours at 37°. Always a blank accompanied each sample. Necessary precautions were taken to note readings under sterile conditions. After the period of incubation, each flask was taken out and the contents titrated against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide. The difference between the sample and the blank gave the activity of the lipase in terms of c. c. of $N/10$ sodium hydroxide. The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I

Optimum pH for lipase using disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer.

Set No.	Oil.	pH .	$N/10$ -sodium hydroxide for		
			Sample.	Blank.	Free acid.
1	1.0 c.c.	2.4	18.0 c.c.	15.9 c.c.	3.1 c.c.
2	1.0	2.8	18.8	14.0	4.8
3	1.0	3.1	16.5	10.8	4.9
4	1.0	4.8	10.2	6.2	5.0
5	1.0	5.2	4.9	4.2	0.7
6	1.0	5.5	3.8	3.3	0.5
7	1.0	5.7	7.1	6.1	1.0
8	1.0	6.2	9.2	9.0	0.2

TABLE II

Optimum pH for lipase using sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer.

Set No.	Oil.	pH .	$N/10$ -sodium hydroxide for		
			Sample.	Blank.	Free acid.
1	1.0 c.c.	1.5	13.8 c.c.	12.9 c.c.	0.9 c.c.
2	1.0	2.9	18.2	10.8	7.9
3	1.0	3.8	25.3	11.5	13.8
4	1.0	4.3	25.2	9.9	15.3
5	1.0	4.8	30.0	10.4	19.6
6	1.0	5.2	12.0	9.5	2.5
7	1.0	5.5	5.0	2.8	2.3
8	1.0	5.7	4.8	3.0	1.6
9	1.0	6.0	3.9	2.8	1.1

TABLE III

Optimum pH for lipase using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer.

Set No.	Oil.	pH .	$N/10$ -sodium hydroxide for		
			Sample.	Blank.	Free acid.
1	1.0 c.c.	3.8	16.2 c.c.	9.1 c.c.	7.1 c.c.
2	1.0	4.1	19.4	8.2	11.2
3	1.0	4.8	23.1	7.8	15.8
4	1.0	4.9	37.9	6.1	31.7
5	1.0	5.5	15.7	5.2	10.5
6	1.0	5.7	11.8	4.8	7.3
7	1.0	5.9	9.5	9.8	5.8
8	1.0	6.0	6.9	2.6	4.3

From the above tables, it is found that in disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer, the optimum p_H is 4.8. In sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer, the optimum p_H is 4.8. In sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer, the optimum p_H is 4.9. It is inferred that the optimum p_H for the hydrolysis of the olive oil by ricinus lipase from castor seed is almost constant, *i. e.*, 4.8 to 4.9 p_H varying slightly according to the buffer used. But at the same time, the percentage hydrolysis of olive oil is greatest in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer and least in phosphate buffer.

Effect of Buffer Concentration on the Hydrolysis of Olive Oil by Lipase.—Each set of the experiments consisted of 1 c. c. of olive oil, 2 c.c. of water, 0.1g. of lipase and varying quantities of acetate buffer of 4.9 p_H and incubated for 24 hours at 37°. Always the blank accompanied each sample. After the period of incubation, the contents of each flask were titrated against *N/10* sodium hydroxide after adding 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol. The results are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Set No.	Oil.	Buffer added.	<i>N/10</i> -sodium hydroxide for		
			Sample.	Blank.	Free acid.
1	1.0 c.c.	1.0 c.c.	30.3 c.c.	1.3 c.c.	29.1 c.c.
2	1.0	2.0	25.0	1.8	23.2
3	1.0	3.0	20.5	2.1	18.4
4	1.0	4.0	18.3	2.3	16.0
5	1.0	5.0	17.4	2.5	14.9
6	1.0	6.0	15.7	3.4	12.3
7	1.0	7.0	14.8	3.8	11.0

From the above table, it is found that the maximum percentage hydrolysis is obtained at the buffer concentration of 1 c. c. and falls gradually as the concentration increases which shows that the percentage hydrolysis goes on decreasing with the increase of buffer concentration.

Effect of Substrate Concentration on the Hydrolysis of Olive Oil by Lipase.—Each set of the experiments consisted of varying quantities of olive oil, 2 c. c. of water, 0.1 g. of lipase and 1 c. c. of acetate buffer of 4.9 p_H , incubated for 24 hours at 37°. After the period of incubation, the contents were titrated against *N/10* sodium hydroxide after the addition of 25 c. c. of neutral alcohol. Each set was accompanied by a blank. The results are given in Table V. From Table V, it is found that the percentage hydrolysis increases as the concentration of the substrate increases from 1 to 3 c.c. and then gradually decreases as the concentration of the oil increases. Therefore, the maximum percentage hydrolysis is obtained when the concentration of the oil is 3 c. c.

TABLE V

Set No.	Oil	N/10-sodium hydroxide for		
		Sample.	Blank.	Free acid.
1	1.0 c.c.	43.0 c.c.	1.2 c.c.	41.8 c.c.
2	2.0	50.4	1.2	49.2
3	3.0	57.3	1.2	56.1
4	4.0	54.4	1.2	53.2
5	5.0	48.2	1.2	47.0
6	6.0	42.5	1.2	41.3

Effect of Enzyme Concentration on the Hydrolysis of Olive Oil by Lipase.—Each set of the experiments consisted of 1 c. c. of olive oil, 2 c. c. of water, 1 c. c. of acetate buffer and varying quantities of the lipase and incubated at 37° for 24 hours. After the period of incubation, the contents were titrated against N/10 sodium hydroxide. Always a blank accompanied each sample. The results are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Set No.	Oil	Enzyme added.	N/10-sodium hydroxide for		
			Sample.	Blank	Free acid.
1	1.0 c.c.	0.1 g.	33.1 c.c.	1.6 c.c.	36.5
2	1.0	0.2	36.3	1.6	39.7
3	1.0	0.3	39.1	1.7	37.4
4	1.0	0.4	40.3	2.0	38.3
5	1.0	0.5	46.2	2.0	44.2
6	1.0	0.6	46.9	2.1	44.8
7	1.0	0.7	52.1	2.3	49.8

From the above table, the percentage hydrolysis of olive oil appears to increase with increase in the concentration of the enzyme.

Effect of Ageing on the Activity of the Lipase.—There are many factors which affect the activity of the enzymes, e. g., heat, light, time, chemicals, etc., most of which can be prevented except the time factor. So, an investigation was carried out to study the effect of ageing on the activity of the lipase.

The hydrolysis of olive oil by lipase was studied from the time of preparation of the lipase up to a period of 4½ months. Each set of the experiments consisted of 1 c. c. of olive oil, 2 c. c. of water, 0.1 g. of lipase and 1 c. c. of acetate buffer and kept in the incubator at 37° for 20 minutes and then titrated against N/10 sodium hydroxide. Always a blank accompanied each sample. The results are given in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Set No.	Time.	Oil.	Diff. bet. the sample & the blank*.	Set No.	Time.	Oil.	Diff. bet. the sample & the blank*.
1	0 min.	1.0 c.c.	7.5 c.c.	14	28 days	1.0 c.c.	19.9
2	20	1.0	7.9	15	71	1.0	17.9
3	40	1.0	7.9	16	78	1.0	10.7
4	1 hr.	1.0	8.4	17	85	1.0	10.2
5	24	1.0	13.7	18	93	1.0	9.8
6	2 days	1.0	23.2	19	100	1.0	8.9
7	3	1.0	23.3	20	114	1.0	8.6
8	4	1.0	23.4	21	121	1.0	7.8
9	5	1.0	23.5	22	134	1.0	6.6
10	6	1.0	24.4	23	142	1.0	6.1
11	8	1.0	24.8	24	150	1.0	3.9
12	11	1.0	20.6	25	155	1.0	2.8
13	16	1.0	20.2	26	160	1.0	0.6

* In terms of c. c. of N/10.NaOH.

From the above table, activity is found to increase up to the 8th day and then it slowly decreases and on the 160th day, it is almost lost. The reason may be due to a small amount of petroleum ether which adheres to the lipase or due to some physical change which may take place in the enzyme after some time.

Preparation of Different Samples of Lipase.—As it was found that petroleum ether-dried lipase did not keep its activity constant, several preparations of lipase were made and the effect of ageing on their activities studied to select a sample which would keep its activity fairly constant for a long time.

So, first petroleum ether extract of the lipase was prepared by the usual method and then three samples were prepared by draining for 2 hours—one with petroleum ether, the other with ethyl ether and the third with boiling acetone. All the three samples were completely dried, sieved through a 60 mesh sieve and the fine powder obtained in each case was used for the experiment.

The activities of the three samples were determined at different intervals of time (Table VIII).

From Table VIII, it is found that in the case of petroleum ether-dried and ether-dried samples, the activity first increases and then falls. In case of acetone-dried sample, it is almost constant throughout even though the activity is very low. So, it can be seen that acetone-dried sample retains its activity fairly constant for an appreciably long time.

TABLE VIII

Set No.	Time.	Lipase added.	Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in terms of N/10. NaOH.		
			Petroleum ether sample.	Ether sample.	Acetone sample.
1	0 min.	0.1 g.	7.5 c.c.	5.2 c.c.	1.4 c.c.
2	20	0.1	7.9	5.8	1.4
3	40	0.1	7.9	5.9	1.4
4	1 hour	0.1	8.4	6.1	1.4
5	24 hours	0.1	18.7	10.2	1.4
6	2 days	0.1	23.2	11.5	1.4
7	3	0.1	23.3	12.1	1.4
8	4	0.1	23.4	14.8	1.4
9	5	0.1	23.5	18.2	1.4
10	6	0.1	24.4	10.5	1.4
11	8	0.1	24.8	15.3	1.4
12	11	0.1	20.5	10.2	1.4
13	15	0.1	20.2	9.2	1.4
14	23	0.1	19.9	8.4	1.4
15	71	0.1	17.9	5.3	1.4
16	78	0.1	10.7	4.6	1.4
17	83	0.1	10.2	3.7	1.4
18	83	0.1	9.8	2.9	1.4
19	100	0.1	8.9	2.7	1.4
20	114	0.1	8.6	1.3	1.4
21	120	0.1	7.8	1.1	1.4
22	134	0.1	6.6	0.8	1.4
23	142	0.1	5.1	1.4	1.4
24	150	0.1	3.9	—	1.4
25	155	0.1	2.8	—	1.4
26	160	0.1	0.5	—	1.4